

NATURAL FLAVONES. PART I. THE CONSTITUTION OF GARDENIN.

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Gardenin was regarded by Stenhouse and Groves to be $C_{14}H_{10}O_6$. Experimental evidence, which has been brought forward in this paper, shows that gardenin has the molecular formula $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$, and is either 5-hydroxy-3 : 6 : 8 : 3' : 4' : 5'-hexamethoxyflavone or its isomer 5-hydroxy-3 : 7 : 8 : 3' : 4' : 5'-hexamethoxyflavone. This is the first instance of a derivative of heptahydroxyflavone found in nature.

Gardenin is the yellow colouring matter present in Dikamali gum, which is a resinous exudation of the leaf-bud of *Gardenia lucida*, Roxb. (= *G. resinifera* Roth or *G. gummifera* Linn.) belonging to the N. O. Rubiaceæ.

Sanskrit writers recommend the gum in fever, dyspepsia, flatulence and chronic skin diseases, while it is much prescribed by Hakims in Bombay in dyspepsia attended with flatulence (Dymock, Warden and Hooper, *Pharm. Ind.*, II. p. 207 ; Dymock, *Pharm. J.*, 1876, 7, 491).

More than eighty years ago Stenhouse reported to the Royal Society of London the presence of a golden yellow crystalline substance in Dikamali gum, which was named gardenin. Flückiger (*Pharm. J.*, 1877, 7, 589) isolated gardenin from the same source and his analytical data agreed with the formula $C_{23}H_{30}O_{10}$. Stenhouse and Groves (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 552), however, observed that pure gardenin melts at $163-64^\circ$, and their analyses agreed with the formula $(C_8H_8O_2)_x$. Further investigation by the same workers (*Annalen*, 1880, 200, 311) indicated that the analytical data were in better agreement with the formula $C_{14}H_{12}O_6$, although they did not determine the molecular weight of the substance. Oxidation of gardenin with nitric acid gave an orange-red crystalline substance, $C_{14}H_{10}O_6$ (m.p. 223°) which was called gardenic acid. Reduction of this substance led to a yellow product, $C_{14}H_{14}O_6$ (m.p. 190°), called hydrogardenic acid, which could be converted by careful oxidation into the parent acid. The latter was suspected to be a quinone and gave a diacetyl derivative, m.p. $230-44^\circ$, on being boiled with acetic acid. The main findings of Stenhouse and Groves may be summarised thus.:

The authors, however, did not propose any definite constitutional formula for gardenin based on the above results.

We took up the investigation of this substance fifty-six years after the last publication of researches on gardenin. The method recommended by Stenhouse and Groves for the isolation of crude gardenin was followed. The process of purification was, however, modified (*vide* Experimental). Our gardenin was found to melt at $161^{\circ}\text{-}62^{\circ}$ (uncorr.) and the melting point could not be raised by crystallisations from different solvents. The elementary analyses of our gardenin gave values which were very close to those found by Stenhouse and Groves, but not identical.

The analytical values obtained by different investigators are as follows:

Flückiger.	Stenhouse and Groves.		Present authors.
	I	II	
C=59.47 (mean)	61.91	60.85	60.16, 60.61 per cent.
H=6.71 (")	5.45	4.75	5.22, 5.3 "

We observed, moreover, that gardenin contains a high percentage of methoxy group, a fact which had escaped the notice of earlier workers. Our analytical data agreed with the formula $(C_7H_7O_3)_2$ for gardenin. A molecular weight determination in benzene by the cryoscopic method did not give reliable results owing to the low solubility of gardenin in this solvent. Stenhouse and Groves had observed that gardenin could be acetylated or benzoyleated, but did not isolate the acetyl or benzoyl derivatives. We found that gardenin gives, under the usual condition of acetylation, a monoacetyl-gardenin, m.p. 136° , which had a mean molecular weight of 454. The parent compound, therefore, must have a molecular weight of about 412. In other words the molecular formula of gardenin must be $C_{21}H_{20}O_9$ or $C_{21}H_{22}O_9$.

Gardenin is insoluble in cold 5% alkali, but dissolves to a yellow

solution on heating. Evidently gardenin possesses weak phenolic properties. The presence of phenolic OH group is further proved by acetylation and reaction with ferric chloride, which imparts an olive-green colour to an alcoholic solution of gardenin. It has no reducing action on alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene or ammoniacal silver nitrate solution. It is optically inactive. Tests for the methylenedioxy group and quinone were negative. A red colour was produced on treating an alcoholic solution of gardenin with magnesium and hydrochloric acid, suggesting that gardenin might belong to the flavone group. Since gardenin contains one hydroxy and six methoxy groups, such a supposition would imply that gardenin is a derivative of heptahydroxyflavone, a representative of which has not, up till now, been found in nature or synthesised. Assuming that gardenin is a flavone, it should be expected to undergo facile hydrolysis by alkali. As a matter of fact 15-20% alkali decomposed gardenin and two different crystalline substances were isolated from the reaction mixture. One of these was found to be identical with trimethylgallic acid. The partial formula for gardenin can, therefore, be represented by (I). This also leads to the acceptance of $C_{21}H_{22}O_9$ as the correct molecular formula for gardenin.

Next we attempted to locate the position of the free hydroxyl group. The stability of an alkaline solution of gardenin to aerial oxidation indicates that the -OH group is not in position 3 of the flavone nucleus. Evidently it must occupy one of the four positions, namely 5, 6, 7 or 8 of the chromone nucleus. That the position 5 might be occupied by the -OH group was suggested by the fact that in partially methylated hydroxyflavones, flavonols and flavanones occurring in nature, the -OH group in position 5 is, as a rule, never found in the methylated condition. It is, moreover, well known that methylation of the hydroxyl group in position 5 proceeds with great difficulty. This was also found to be the case with gardenin. A positive proof of the position of the hydroxyl group was, however, furnished by an examination of the condensation product of gardenin with stannic chloride. The ratio of Sn: Cl in

the complex salt was found to be nearly 1 : 3. Pfeiffer (*Annalen*, 1913, 398, 137) has shown that a compound of the type (II) reacts with stannic chloride in benzene solution forming (III), whereas if the -OH group be not adjacent to the -CO-R group, then double compounds of the type $\text{HO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{R}\cdot\text{SnCl}_4$ are formed. The formation of the SnCl_3 -complex definitely establishes the position of the OH group, which must occupy position 5.

The positions of the remaining three methoxy groups now remain to be settled. There are four possibilities, namely (IV), (V), (VI) or (VII). Compounds of the type (IV) and (V) on demethylation would give rise to

heptahydroxyflavones having three contiguous OH groups in positions 5, 6 and 7. Such compounds should be expected to give a positive Bargellini's test. In fact an alcoholic solution of demethylated gardenin gave a brown precipitate with sodium amalgam, but not the green precipitate characteristic of flavones having OH groups in positions 5, 6, and 7 (Bargellini, *Gazzetta*, 1919, 49, ii, 47; Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1030; Baker, Nodzu and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 83). It seems, therefore, unlikely that gardenin should have the structure (IV) or (V). The choice consequently must lie between (VI) and (VII).

The second product of alkaline hydrolysis of gardenin was also examined with a view to throw more light on the constitution of gardenin. This substance separates as a deep red dipotassium salt from the reaction mixture. Treatment with hydrochloric acid liberated a chocolate coloured compound, m.p. 158-60°, which is fairly soluble in water. It has acidic reactions and gives a dirty violet colour with ferric chloride. On reduction with sulphurous acid it is converted into a yellow compound, m.p. 175-76°. This

is also acidic to litmus and gives a violet ferric chloride reaction. Unlike the parent substance, however, it reduced alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene in the cold (*cf.* Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ray Com. Vol.*, 1933, p. 65) showing the presence of -OH groups in *ortho*- or *para*-positions to one another. On keeping it exposed to the atmosphere it is slowly transformed into the parent substance, m. p. 158-60°. The analytical data of these two substances as also their properties are in agreement with the formulae (VIII) and (IX) or (X) and (XI) or their isomers. We are attempting to synthesise compound (IX).

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

Incidentally we have examined the so-called 'gardenic acid' of Stenhouse and Groves and its reduction product, 'hydrogardenic acid.' 'Gardenic acid' prepared by us by following the method of earlier workers was found to melt at 222-24° (*lit.* 223°) and agreed with the formula $C_{20}H_{18}O_9$. It liberated iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution showing that it is a quinone. We propose the name gardeninone for this compound, which is evidently formed by loss of a methyl group. From the mother-liquor (acetic acid) of gardeninone we obtained a small quantity of another product, m. p. 238-40°, which was not further examined and which is probably the so-called 'diacetyl gardenic acid' of Stenhouse and Groves. Further oxidation of gardeninone by nitric acid (*d* 1.25) led to a colourless compound, m. p. 96-97°, which was identified as 1-nitro-3:4:5-trimethoxybenzene. This compound is no doubt formed by

the nitration of the side-chain of gardeninone, since trimethylgallic acid also produced the same compound under identical experimental conditions. Prolonged contact with nitric acid gave a compound, m. p. 116-17°, which is believed to be 1 : 2-dinitro-3 : 4 : 5-trimethoxybenzene, since it responded to the colour reactions of *o*-dinitro-compounds (Bose and Sundar Ranı, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 687).

Reduction of gardeninone by sulphurous acid gave a deep yellow crystalline compound, m. p. 184-85° (the 'hydrogardenic acid' of Stenhouse and Groves). This quinol, called gardeninol by us, gave the tests of a polyhydroxybenzene derivative (Bose, *loc. cit.*) and formed a diacetyl derivative. Assuming the structure (VI) or (VII) for gardenin, the formulæ for gardeninone and gardeninol may be represented by (XII) or (XIII) and (XIV) or (XV) respectively.

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Purification of Gardenin.—Crude gardenin, obtained by the method of Stenhouse and Groves (*loc. cit.*), was washed with cold carbon disulphide to remove the greater portion of adhering resins. It was then dissolved in chloroform and diluted with rectified spirit, when yellow needles separated out. This process was repeated three or four times till the m.p. became constant. Finally it was crystallised from absolute alcohol: m.p.

161-62°. (Found : C, 60.16, 60.61 ; H, 5.22, 5.3 ; OMe, 44.24. $C_{21}H_{23}O_6$ requires C, 60.29 ; H, 5.26 ; OMe, 44.49 per cent).

Acetylgardenin.—A mixture of gardenin (0.2 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.), acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) was gently boiled for 5 hours under reflux. The acetyl derivative was separated in the usual manner and crystallised from benzene-ligroin in very pale yellow needles, m.p. 136°. [Found : C, 59.55 ; H, 5.26 ; acetyl, 8.06 ; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 460.4, 448. $C_{22}H_{24}O_{10}$ requires C, 60.0 ; H, 5.22 ; acetyl, 9.34 per cent. M.W., 460).

Hydrolysis of Gardenin.—Gardenin (1 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (15%, 20 c.c.) for 7 hours. Gardenin gradually went into solution with an orange colour which afterwards turned red with the progress of the reaction. The mixture was left overnight and the red crystalline precipitate, which had separated out, was filtered off the next day and washed twice with absolute alcohol. This was then dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and the solution was diluted with alcohol when the red potassium salt crystallised out. This process was repeated four times and the compound was then analysed. It could not be completely freed from a trace of potassium carbonate, which was detected in the usual manner. (Found : K, 29.09. $C_9H_8O_6K_2$ requires K, 27.08 per cent).

Isolation of Trimethylgallic Acid.—The filtrate from the potassium salt was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was washed with a little cold water and then crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, sublimed in high vacuum and the sublimate crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, when colourless needles were obtained ; m.p. 165-66°. It dissolved in cold sodium bicarbonate solution and did not depress the m.p. of synthetic trimethylgallic acid.

Isolation of the Second Product of Hydrolysis.—The red potassium salt was dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and just acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (congo-red). The solution was allowed to concentrate in vacuum over sulphuric acid and potassium hydroxide. The dark brown crystals, which separated out, were collected, washed with a little cold water and recrystallised from water at room temperature in a similar manner. It formed dark chocolate crystals, m.p. 158-60°. The substance was acidic to litmus and gave a dirty violet colour with ferric chloride. It was indifferent towards alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene. (Found : C, 50.50, 50.56 ; H, 3.9, 3.55 ; OMe, 14.65. $C_9H_8O_6$ requires C, 50.94 ; H, 3.77 ; OMe, 14.62 per cent).

*Reduction of the above Compound : Formation of Tetrahydroxy-*o*-methoxyacetophenone.*—0.2 G. of the above substance was dissolved in rectified spirit and the solution saturated with sulphur dioxide. The mixture was left overnight in a cool place and then concentrated on the water-bath, when a brown-yellow crystalline compound separated out. This was washed with a little cold water and dried (0.13 g.). It was sublimed in high vacuum (150°-55°/0.05 mm.) and then crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 175-76°. It gave a violet ferric chloride reaction and a positive test with alkaline *o*-dinitrobenzene. (Found : C, 50.80; H, 4.98. OMe, 14.55. $C_9H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 50.47; H, 4.67; OMe, 14.49 per cent).

Gardeninone.—Finely powdered gardenin (1 g.) was placed in a basin previously cooled in ice-water. To this was added nitric acid (*d* 1.25, 10 g.) The mixture was thoroughly stirred. The yellow colour of gardenin changed to orange in 2-3 minutes and finally became deep orange-red. The reaction was continued for about 10 minutes and the completion of the reaction was ascertained by observing the crystals under the microscope, the absence of the yellow crystals of gardenin indicating the end. The temperature of the reaction should not exceed 25°, otherwise the yield is diminished owing to further oxidation of gardeninone. Temperatures below 10° again make the reaction very sluggish. The crude gardeninone was thoroughly washed with water till free from nitric acid and dried (0.5 g.). This was then crystallised from glacial acetic acid as orange crystals, m.p. 222-24°. (Found : C, 60.0; H, 4.72; OMe, 38.34. $C_{20}H_{18}O_9$ requires C, 59.70; H, 4.48; OMe, 38.56 per cent).

Oxidation of Gardeninone.—Gardeninone was boiled with nitric acid (*d* 1.25) till the former went into solution and the solution became colourless. The clear solution was then rapidly cooled and kept in an ice chamber for several hours. The colourless crystals which separated out were collected and crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol. It was further purified by sublimation at 90°-100°/0.05 mm.; m.p. 97°.

Nitration of Trimethylgallie Acid.—Trimethylgallie acid was boiled with nitric acid (*d* 1.25) till effervescence ceased and the acid went into solution. On cooling a crystalline substance was obtained, which was purified as described above. It melts at 97° and did not depress the m.p. of the compound described above. The m.p. of 1-nitro-3 : 4 : 5-trimethoxybenzene given in literature is 99-100°.

Formation of 1 : 2-Dinitro-3 : 4 : 5-trimethoxybenzene.—If gardenin be boiled with an excess of nitric acid of the same strength for a longer period

and the clear colourless solution is allowed to stand for several days at room temperature, a crystalline substance is obtained. On crystallisation from dilute alcohol, it forms almost colourless crystals, m. p. 116-17°. It gives a violet colour with uric acid and alkali, showing that it is an *ortho*-dinitro compound, which cannot be anything else but the above compound.

Gardeninol.—Through a suspension of gardeninone in rectified spirit, a current of sulphur dioxide was passed till the quinone went into solution. On concentration and cooling yellow crystals were obtained. Recrystallised from alcohol it formed yellow needles, m. p. 184-85° (the m. p. of 'hydrogardenic acid' of Stehhouse and Groves is 190°). It is not acidic to litmus but dissolves in dilute alkali with a brown colour. The ferric chloride reaction is deep olive-green. *o*-Dinitrobenzene gives a dirty violet colour in presence of cold dilute alkali. (Found: C, 59.29; H, 5.21. $C_{20}H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 59.4; H, 4.95 per cent).

Diacetylgardeninol.—The compound was prepared in the usual manner and formed colourless crystals (alcohol), m.p. 146-47°. (Found: C, 59.03; H, 4.65; OMe, 31.42. $C_{24}H_{24}O_{11}$ requires C, 59.02, H, 4.92; OMe, 31.77 per cent).

Methylgardenin.—Gardenin (1 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and sodium hydroxide (25%, 8 c.c.) was added. The mixture was mechanically stirred and 18 g. of dimethylsulphate and 24 c.c. of sodium hydroxide (25%) were added drop by drop from dropping funnels, so that the solution remained faintly alkaline. After the completion of the reaction, the mixture was diluted with a large volume of water and the precipitate filtered off. The crude methylgardenin still contained considerable quantity of the parent substance and was again methylated in a similar manner. This process was repeated three times. The pale yellow product was finally crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 102° (after drying for 3 hours at 50°-60° in vacuum). (Found: C, 60.60*; H, 5.34. $C_{22}H_{24}O_9$ requires C, 61.11; H, 5.55 per cent).

Demethylation of Gardenin.—A mixture of gardenin (0.5 g.), hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 8 c.c.) and phenol (1 c.c.) was gently boiled for 1.5 hours. The product was poured into very dilute sodium bisulphite solution and

* Highly methylated flavones usually give low values (*cf.* Heap and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 73; Baker, Nodzu, and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1929, 81; Prenderberg, Pickettocher and Wenner, *Annalen*, 1925, 442, 314).

the yellow precipitate collected and washed with water. Although it is easily soluble in hot alcohol and acetone, attempts to obtain it in the crystalline form have not been successful. It decomposed above 300° and gave a brown precipitate with sodium amalgam in alcoholic solution.

Condensation of Gardenin with Stannic Chloride.—Gardenin (0.5 g) was dissolved in dry benzene and stannic chloride (1 c.c.) quickly added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours. The red precipitate was quickly filtered off, washed with dry benzene and dried over sulphuric acid, paraffin and potash in a desiccator. It does not melt below 335° . (Found: Sn : Cl = 1 : 2.9. Calc. Sn : Cl = 1 : 3).

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